

Ecological Influence on Mathematical Learning

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ABSTRACT : In mathematical learning students' linguistic abilities play an important role for conceptual processing of mathematical ideas. Cultural and environmental factors shape the representations that are required for mathematical learning. Since mathematics is treated as language, it has own vocabulary, syntax, semantics and discourse properties. Ecolinguistic interaction is the fundamental condition for mathematical learning. Use of environmental situations for mathematical learning situations was explored by teachers at different level when they were interviewed. It was argued that an individual constructs knowledge through interaction with their environment throughout life. Environment plays a significant role in child cognition. Mathematical learning from environment comes in the open and requires some conditionalities. Mathematical learning is the engaging activity of the learner either in classroom or elsewhere.

Key words: Ecology, Environment, Mathematical learning, Linguistic, Language.

1. Introduction

It is widely accepted that students' linguistic abilities play an important role in their learning and conceptual processing of academic subjects. This role is particularly important in the domain of mathematics, where students have to use their linguistic abilities before conceptualizing a problem in mathematical terms, so that they can arrive at a correct numerical representation and problem solution. In this sense, achievement in mathematics is influenced by the student's proficiency in the language of instruction (Zepp, 1981). Miura (2001) argued that students'

mathematics understanding is influenced by the cultural factors that shape the representations that are not found within the classroom. These factors include the characteristics of the language of instruction, and the characteristics of the mathematical terms that are specific to that language. The representations are of two types: instructional, which refer to classroom discourse, and cognitive, which refer to the individual student's conceptual representations.

Word problems have traditionally been difficult for many people. In many instances, individuals who seem to lack adequate

computational skills in solving word problems demonstrate these skills when problems are presented in numerical form. A variety of explanations coming from research in elementary arithmetic has been offered to account for how the wording of arithmetic story-problems influences performance. Some researchers have focused on the semantic structure of addition and subtraction word problems (Carpenter & Moser, 1982, 1983; Riley & Greeno, 1988; Riley, Greeno, & Heller, 1983). Other researchers have emphasized the mathematics basic ability or knowledge required to represent the semantic relations (Gelman & Greeno, 1989; Resnick, 1989; Riley & Greeno, 1988). Others offer linguistic explanations (Cummins, 1991; Cummins, Kintsch, Reusser, & Weimer, 1988; Hudson, 1983) in which the difficulty is attributed to comprehension aspects that have to do with language ambiguity and the abstract nature of mathematical language. Although some authors have suggested that syntactic simplification may help children's understanding of word problems (De Corte, Verschaffel, & De Win., 1985), syntactic details seem to be of little use to students for distinguishing situations presented in word problems (Marshall, 1995). Nevertheless, Cummins et al. (1988) found that children miscomprehended more word problems that contained ambiguous and abstract language than problems worded in simpler language terms. They also found that solution errors were related to the ability to recall the statement of the problem correctly. In other words, their study suggests that appropriate representation of word problems is highly language and textbase dependent. Similarly, Kintsch and Greeno (1985) also argued that the root of arithmetic word problem difficulty can be traced back to text

comprehension. They believed that the nature of comprehension itself is determined by the purposes for which the text is read. Thus, there are textual aspects that warrant the use of the specific knowledge structures and operations required to arrive at the correct solution. In her socio-linguistic view of L2 reading, Bernhardt (1991) claimed that the pre-set nature of reading is determined by the nature of texts and the learned ways of dealing with such texts in the L1 context. In the case of word problems, the text is already pre-set for mathematical understanding. That is, the students must approach this type of text within the mathematical framework. They must know that the words have mathematical meaning, regardless of the 'real world' situation presented in the text.

2. Mathematical Language

Mathematics is a language most of which are not recognized as such by any mathematicians because we have no specialist's knowledge of the language. The language like nature of mathematics has a great importance, as it is the most important part of our understanding with the physical universe. Mathematics is derived from everyday language by the introduction of various special conventions that permit a precision of statement and of inferences not otherwise attainable.

Mathematical language has its own vocabulary, syntax, semantic and discourse properties. Vocabulary of mathematics is rather more or less stable. In terms of Vocabulary, mathematics includes Words that are specific to the domain (e.g., coefficient, denominator, etc.), and day to day words that take on a specific meaning within the context of mathematics (e.g., equal, rational, table, column,

etc.). Competence in this specific vocabulary is crucial to students' mathematical understanding especially as they progress to higher grades. It means that they have to learn that the terms are related to the context in which they occur. Additionally, students have to learn another vocabulary that includes the extensive system of mathematical Symbols, which have their own meaning within the mathematical context. These symbols increase in conceptual density as students move up in the Ladder of the curriculum. Students must also understand that there is a lack of a one to one correspondence between mathematical symbols and the words they represent, and the role of logical connectors (e.g., if...then, if and only if, but, etc.) which indicate the nature of the relationship between parts of the text (Crandall, Dale, Rhodes, & Spanos, 1987; Kessler, Quinn, & Hayes, 1985).

Mathematics itself is universal. The elegance of a proof, the consistency of a set of axioms, the nature of conjecture, the validity of an argument etc. are shown a common frame of reference by any mathematician from anywhere of the globe and can be formalized in a strongly formalized notation which is universally accepted. The languages in which the mathematicians discuss mathematics may differ, but about mathematics there is a total agreement (e.g. A problem may be solved algebraically or geometrically).

3. Ecology of Language

The Ecology of Language may be defined as the study of interactions between any given language and its environment. The true environment of a language is the society that uses it as one of its codes. Language exists only in the minds of its users, and it only functions in

relating these users to one another and to nature, i.e. their social and natural environment. Part of its ecology is therefore Psychological: its interaction with other languages in the minds of bi- and multilingual speakers. Another part of its ecology is Sociological: its interaction with the society in which it functions as a medium of communication. The ecology of a language is determined primarily by the people who learn it, use it, preserve it and transmit it to others.

The ecology of language relates to cognitive development and human interaction, the maintenance and survival of languages, the promotion of linguistic diversity, language policy and planning, language acquisition, language evolution, language ideology, the ecology of (multilingual) classroom interaction and the ecologies of literacy and discourses. Indeed, it has been noted that there is an 'infinite world of possibilities' for language ecology (Barron et al., 2002).

The study of ecology of language is the study of diversity within specific social settings where the processes of language use create, reflect and challenge particular hierarchies and hegemonies, however transient these might be. It will be at once apparent that all of the themes — language, literacy and learning are central to our understanding of education and an ecological perspective demands a particular view of education and classroom practice as situated and localised.

The ecology of languages should be an ecology based on ecosystems and the relations among these ecosystems, because the basic unit is not language but always *the-language-in-its-context*. Making a mathematical language sustainable in a sociocultural ecosystem will mean balancing a complex organisation in the

framework of which the corresponding code can be provided with a functional niche that is sufficient to guarantee an adequate homeostasis. Sustainability is clearly ecosystemic and dynamic. From this perspective, it should be clear that languages are thus not simple objects but rather complex ones, emergences produced and maintained at the meeting point of different dimensions. A real mathematical language is not only its grammar or its lexis but also living human cognition, interaction, and identification. The linguistic code, therefore, will register the events of these planes, and will evolve in accordance with them, naming things that we want to name, and being used or not in the circumstances which we desire. In this sense, languages are in our hands and we are in the hands of our own vital circumstances. The ecosystemic approach is, then, indispensable and essential.

4. Mathematical Learning from Nature

In using cultural influences from existing peoples, one can speculate that our ancestors, in learning how to count, employed a limited discrete number vocabulary and supplemented it with a rich variety of many words. Such vocabularies were focused on what they believed important. It is apparent that as a society grows and obtains more sophisticated needs, number vocabularies and their accompanying numerals become more extensive and complex. An extensive, precise number vocabulary is necessary when communication is remote, impersonal and over a distance.

It is argued that an individual constructs knowledge through interaction with their environment throughout life, and to social constructivism based on Vygotsky's model of social cognition that have come to dominate

thinking amongst those concerned with the pedagogy of lifelong learning. The predominant Vygotskian idea concerns the effect of culture on individual development; it provides both the source of knowledge and the tools of intellectual adaptation. According to Vygotsky, linguistic interaction is the fundamental condition for learning.

The traditional way of learning mathematics is to count and to write numbers, associating numbers often with dots or line on a piece of paper or less often with actual objects. Later on, the learner involved on adding, subtracting, multiplying and dividing numbers. Such learning is almost invariably dissociated completely from the natural world of the child, where, in practice the numbers are embedded in the word used by the community to which the child belongs. The consequence of this is that the child does not associate numbers with life around him. Teachers tend to keep closely to textbooks. So they do not usually talk about numbers or measures in a way which is familiar to the child in his out of such experience. The child has to learn the symbol and attach to them the worlds he has never met before in his home or cultural life.

There is a need for assuming the impact of environment on mathematics education. Learning situation(s), in no way, can be ignored. Environmental learning comes in the open and requires some conditionalities to be identified. Assuming the environment to provide some essentials of environment, one can formulate a problem in learning environment. The latter becomes then part of the kinetics. This, when mathematize to a certain extent, leads to the beginning of mathematizing of ecological scenarios in respect of learning.

Mathematics education has some complex characters and there is a need to focus in the context of contemporary trends. Environment plays a significant role in child cognition. Environmental learning comes in the open and requires some conditionalities. Learning being the engaging activity of the taker (student), whether be in the classroom or elsewhere has to be considered in depth. On account of wide ranging of character, environmental resources provide enormous data that are in no way empirical. To explore the ecological scenarios, school teachers at different levels were interviewed. Some of the scenarios that were explored by them are mentioned below.

In the plant world, the arrangement of leaves around a stem or seeds in a sunflower, form recurring numerical patterns. These patterns are intimately linked with the “golden number”. The curl of a drying fern exhibit types of a spiral arc.

In the animal and insect kingdoms, coat patterns and wing markings can be studied using mathematics, specifically by means of properties and solutions of reaction-diffusion equations. Reaction-diffusion equations describe the interaction between chemicals that, depending on conditions, may produce spots, stripes patterns. There are fascinating mathematical problems.

Dispersion of light may occur almost anywhere under right circumstances and may be described in mathematical terms at varying levels of complexity. The rainbow is formed by sunlight dispersed in preferential directions by near spherical raindrops.

Waves on the surface of puddles, ponds, lakes or oceans are governed by mathematical

relationships between their speed, their wavelength, and the depth of the water etc. The waves produced by ships or ducks generate strikingly similar patterns relative to their size. Sand dunes are beautiful examples of waves. They can occur on a scale of centimeters to kilometers and like surface waves on bodies of water, it is only the waveform that actually moves.

In the past several decades, educators have adopted a pedagogical philosophy that connects instructional practices and curricula to local communities. The approach recasts the role of subject areas in rural schools as helping to explain, understand, and improve local communities and places. The literature on place-based pedagogy reveals a scattering of methodologies and activities to date. The thematic patterns that are so far identified: (a) cultural studies that engage students in learning about their local culture and history; (b) nature studies that focus students on local natural resources; (c) real-world problem solving that involves students in solving community and local problems; (d) internships and entrepreneurial opportunities that engage students in building the economic base of their communities; and (e) induction into community processes where students are engaged in community decision making.

5. Conclusion

To understand the world in which we live, we first make observations and measurements and then we arrange our results and searches for relationships. We generalize by finding a pattern that is shared by our different results and by ignoring special differences. The general

pattern thus obtain is not identical with any of its special cases but it is an abstraction of all of them.

The use of culturally specific resources to achieve the conventional aims of mathematical learning is still a very open question. On one hand, the existence of fundamentally different networks of image schemata calls into serious question the use of isolated materials from the nature in promotion of educational objectives. On the other hand, without presenting ideas from fundamentally different image schemata, it is not possible to illustrate the way in which conventional mathematics developed in a particular way that could have been different.

From the above discussion it is very important for children to give a rich variety of linguistic situations with ecological aspects in order to learn the appropriate mathematical operations that different environmental situations require. In mathematical learning the objects of communication exist independently and can be pointed out and scanned with one's eyes. The objects of mathematical exchange, even if already constructed, are featured as something that can perhaps be represented with visual means, but never really shown. Mathematical communication is likely to be hindered by considerable differences in interlocutors' use of words.

References

- Barron, C., Bruce, N., and Nunan, D. (2002). Knowledge and Discourse. Towards an Ecology of Language, Longman, London.
- Bernhardt, E. B. (1991). *Reading development in second language: theoretical, empirical, and classroom perspectives*. Norwood, NJ: Ablex.
- Bhowmik, H. (2010). Impact of Linguistics in Mathematical Learning. *Sikshachintan* (vol-4, 149-154), R. K. Mission Sikshanamandira, Belurmath, India.
- Bialystok, E. (1991). Letters, sound and symbols: Changes in children's understanding of written language. *Applied Psycholinguistics*, 12(1), 75-89.
- Cummins, D. D., Kintsch, W., Reusser, K., & Weimer, R. (1988). The role of understanding in solving word problems. *Cognitive Psychology*, 20(4), 405-438.
- Hiebert, J., & Carpenter, T. P. (1992). Learning and teaching with understanding. In D. A. Grouws (Ed.), *Handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning* (65-97). New York: Macmillan.
- Kintsch, W., & Greeno, J. G. (1985). Understanding and solving word arithmetic problems. *Psychological Review*.
- Miura, I. T. (2001). The influence of language on mathematical representations. In A. A. Cuoco, & F. R. Curcio (Eds.), *The roles of representation in school mathematics* (pp. 53-62). Reston, VA: National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.
- Muhlhausler, P. (2003). *Language of Environment, A course in Ecolinguistics*. Battlebridge, UK.
- O'Halloran, K. L. (2005). *Mathematical discourse: Language, symbolism and visual images*. NY: Continuum.
- Reed, M. B. (1984). The influence of linguistic factors upon mathematics achievement among second-language learners. *International Journal for Mathematics Education in Science and Technology*, 15, 437-445.
- Reese, L., Garnier, H., Gallimore, R., & Glodenberg, C. (2000). Longitudinal analysis of the antecedents of emergent Spanish literacy and middle-school English reading achievement of Spanish-speaking students. *American Educational Research Journal*, 37(3), 633-662.
- Rehder, B. (1999). Detecting unsolvable algebra word problems. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 91(4), 669-683.
- Resnick, L. (1989). *Knowing, learning, and instruction: essays in honor of Robert Glaser*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Reusser, K., & Stebler, R. (1997). Every word problem has a solution: The social rationality of mathematical

- modeling in schools. *Learning and Instruction*, 7(4), 309-327.
- Riley, M. G., & Greeno, J. G. (1988). Developmental analysis of understanding language about quantities and of solving problems. *Cognition and Instruction*, 5(1), 49-101.
- Riley, M. G., Greeno, J. G. & Heller, J. I. (1983). Development of children's problem solving ability in arithmetic. In H. Ginsburg (Ed.), *The development of mathematical thinking*, (pp. 153-200). NY: Academic.
- Zepp, R. A. (1981). Relationship between mathematics achievement and various English language proficiencies. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 12, 59-70.
- Wardhaugh, R. (2010). *An Introduction to Sociolinguistics*. 6th ed. Willey- Blackwell.

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